

EFFECTS OF TIMED PRACTICE DRILLS ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS OF GRADE EIGHT LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to determine the effects of timed practice drills on the academic performance in mathematics of grade eight learners. Specifically, it focused on the significant difference between the level of academic performance in mathematics between students exposed to non-timed practice drills (NTPD) and those students exposed to timed practice drills (TPD). A quasi-experimental design was used. The study was analyzed using Analysis of Variance. Data were collected from Grade 8 learners of Valencia National High School. A mathematics assessment was used to measure the academic performance in mathematics of the students both in pre-test and post-test between NTPD group and TPD group. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant difference between the level of academic performance in mathematics of the students exposed to NTPD and TPD at $p < 0.05$. This implies that the level of academic performance in mathematics of the Grade 8 learners has improved when exposed to the timed practice drills compared to those under NTPD.

Keywords: *Academic performance, Mathematics, Timed practice drills*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is an essential subject, providing students with the foundational skills and knowledge necessary for success in everyday life. In particular, the concepts of integers and fractions form fundamental building blocks of mathematical understanding, laying the

groundwork for more advanced mathematical topics. Recognizing the significance of these concepts, educators and researchers have sought effective instructional methods to enhance students' mathematical proficiency, with a focus on improving academic performance.

The learning gap in Mathematics among students has widened as a result of the recent pandemic. According to a study conducted by Torres (2021), students need remediation activities before moving on to new classes because of the decline in math learning. There is a growing learning gap in Mathematics, thus, it is important to consistently monitor students' performance in mathematics, as it is considered a key subject for developing analytical and logical problem-solving abilities that are useful in real-life situations.

Given the learning loss caused by the pandemic, teachers are faced with students' poor Mathematics performance, which would ultimately lead to a negative performance in the subject when students move to higher levels. The problems faced by teachers, administrators, and other stakeholders with the mathematics performance of students need to be addressed. Steps can be taken to solve these issues, such as adopting differentiated instruction, providing additional support to students who are struggling, and using technology to enhance remote learning (Aguhayon et al, 2023).

According to Manalaysay (2021), mathematics drill practice can improve mastery of the fundamental processes, and as mastery grows, an individual will be able to apply it to even the most basic daily and professional settings. It implies that instructional methods are essential to the teaching and learning process. It improves students' memory capacity and adds excitement to the teaching and learning process (Tabor, n.d.). More so, the use of drill can motivate students at the start of every discussion (Lozano, 2019).

Timed practice drills involve presenting students with a series of mathematical problems within a specified time limit, encouraging rapid recall of concepts and fostering fluency in mathematical operations. This teaching approach aims to strengthen their computational skills, mental agility, and problem-solving abilities by engaging learners in repeated exposure to integer and fraction problems under timed conditions.

This study investigated the effects of timed practice drills in integers and fractions on the academic performance in mathematics of regular Grade Eight learners at Valencia National High School. The study sought to expand the existing knowledge on effective mathematics teaching by exploring the effects of this instructional method and to provide insights for educators and policymakers on the potential advantages of integrating timed practice drills into teaching strategies.

Through an analysis of students' academic performance data, including pre- and post-assessments, this study sought to explore whether the implementation of timed practice drills in integers and fractions leads to significant improvements in students' academic performance in mathematics.

If timed practice drills prove to be effective, they can be integrated into regular mathematics instruction to enhance students' performance in integers and fractions, thereby strengthening their mathematical foundation and preparing them for more advanced mathematical concepts.

Research Questions

This study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of the students' academic performance in mathematics in terms of pre-test and post-test assessments between non-timed practice drills (NTPD) and timed practice drills (TPD)?
2. Is there a significant difference on the level of academic performance in mathematics between the NTPD and TPD in the pre-test and post-test assessment?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a quasi-experimental research design, specifically the nonequivalent pre-test and post-test assessment. This design was selected instead of a true experimental design due to the nature of the study, which was conducted in a traditional educational setting with pre-existing classes that were already formed before the study started. It has two groups, NTPD group and TPD group and two treatment groups.

Students under NTPD group were not subjected to the timed drill practice, while students under the TPD group were subjected to timed practice drills.

The researcher gave all participants a pre-test that covered topics suitable for Grade Eight regular class students. All participants under the TPD group were given a 10-item drill answered within five (5) minutes daily.

All drills, pre-tests, and post-tests were answered in written form. The post-test assessment was administered at the end of Week 6.

Research Locale and Participants

The study was conducted in Valencia National High School, Valencia City, Bukidnon for six consecutive weeks through face-to-face classes. The participants were Grade Eight students under the regular class. Names and other personal identifiers of the participants were not recorded.

The sampling procedure used in the study is stratified sampling. A 50-item quiz was given to all Grade Eight regular class sections. Two sections with the lowest mean were

selected as the participants of the study. 84 Grade Eight students were selected as research participants.

One section was assigned as the NTPD Group and the other section as TPD Group. The results of the test were interpreted by comparing the results before and after exposure to daily timed practice drills.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study involved three phases. Phase I was for acquiring all necessary documents to start the experimentation, which included approval letters, consent from parents of the participants, and preparation of test questionnaires used for choosing the research participants, for pre-test and post-test assessments as well as the preparation of different sets of 10-item quizzes for the daily timed practice drill. The TPD group was given five (5) minutes to answer the drills.

The Phase II of the data gathering process included the administration of pre-test to the NTPD and TPD group. All groups were given twenty (20) minutes to answer a 30-item quiz. Phase III included administering the post-test assessments at the end of Week 6, all groups were given twenty (20) minutes to answer a 30-item quiz on the same topic.

The statistical tool used in this study is the Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA). The ANCOVA determined if the groups performed differently on the pre-test and post-test.

Instrumentation

A mathematics assessment examination was administered to the participants before and after the intervention period to measure their academic performance. The researcher used textbooks of regular Grade 8 students in Valencia National High School as the basis in preparing the drill questions. The assessment was scored according to established guidelines or rubrics to obtain numerical scores representing participants' performance in integers and fractions.

The researcher designed Drill Worksheets as the data collection instrument for this study. Thirty-item worksheets for the pre- and post-tests and ten-item worksheets for the daily timed practice drills were used. The daily drill was answered for five (5) minutes and pre- and post-tests were answered for twenty (20) minutes.

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics were calculated for all 84 participating students' pre-test and post-test scores.

Table 1. Descriptors, Grading Scale, and Remarks (DepEd Order No. 8 s.2015)

DESCRIPTOR	GRADING SCALE	REMARKS
Outstanding	90-100	Passed
Very Satisfactory	85-89	Passed
Satisfactory	80-84	Passed
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	Passed
Did Not Meet Expectations	Below 75	Failed

Table 1 shows the Descriptors, grading scale, and remarks used in analyzing the scores of the students in the pre-test and post-test assessment.

Table 2. Level of Academic Performance of Grade 8 Students in Pre-test Assessment

Range	TPD GROUP			NTPD GROUP		
	f	%	Interpretation	f	%	Interpretation
90% - 100%	0	0%	Very High	0	0%	Very High
86% - 89%	0	0%	High	0	0%	High
80% - 85%	0	0%	Moderate	0	0%	Moderate
75% - 79%	1	2.22%	Low	0	0%	Low
<75%	44	97.78%	Very Low	39	100%	Very Low
Total	45	100%		39	100%	
	Mean = 57.26 (Very Low)			Mean = 51.45 (Very Low)		

The results in Table 2 indicate that both the Timed Practice Drills (TPD) and Non-Timed Practice Drills (NTPD) groups performed poorly in their pre-test assessments, with mean scores of 57.26% and 51.45%, respectively. These scores fall under the “Did Not Meet Expectations” (DNME) category, highlighting the substantial gaps in students’ foundational knowledge in mathematics.

The data further shows that nearly all students in both groups scored below 75%, with 97.78% of the TPD group and 100% of the NTPD group failing to achieve a satisfactory level.

Table 3. Level of Academic Performance of Grade 8 Students in Post-test Assessment

Range	TPD GROUP			NTPD GROUP		
	f	%	Interpretation	f	%	Interpretation
90% - 100%	18	40.00%	Very High	0	0%	Very High
86% - 89%	5	11.11%	High	0	0%	High
80% - 85%	11	24.44%	Moderate	0	0%	Moderate
75% - 79%	11	24.44%	Low	0	0%	Low
<75%	0	0%	Very Low	39	100%	Very Low
Total	45	100%		39	100%	
	Mean = 84.30 (Moderate)			Mean = 52.91 (Very Low)		

The post-test results reveal an improvement in the academic performance of the students in the Timed Practice Drills (TPD) group, with a mean score of 84.30%, categorizing them as “Satisfactory”. There were students (40%) that attained an “Outstanding” rating (90-100 interval), while 11.11% and 24.44% of the students achieved “Very Satisfactory” (86-89) and “Satisfactory” (80-85) performance levels, respectively.

No students scored below 75, demonstrating the positive impact of timed practice drills on their academic performance in the subject. On the other hand, the Non-Timed Practice Drills (NTPD) group did not show any significant improvement, with a mean post-test score of 52.91%, where all students remained within the “Did Not Meet Expectations” (DNME) category.

Table 4: ANCOVA of Performance Posttest Scores

Group	Mean	SD	N		
TPD	17.18	2.691	45		
NTPD	15.44	3.478	39		
Total	16.37	3.184	84		
Source	SS	Df	MS	F	Sig
Group	1381.094	1	1381.094	105.780	0.000
Pretest (Covariate)	248.440	1	248.440	19.0280	0.000
Error	1057.56	81	13.056		
Total	39960.000	84			

The results presented in Table 4 indicate a significant difference in post-test scores between NTPD and TPD groups, with a p-value less than 0.05 ($p = 0.000$). This implies that the mean of TPD group is significantly higher than that of the NTPD group. The significant difference in post-test scores provides sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, affirming that timed practice drill improved students' academic performance.

DISCUSSION

The results shown in Table 2 have several implications for mathematics instruction, particularly in designing interventions to improve students' computational fluency and problem-solving skills. Studies indicate that students' prior knowledge significantly affects their ability to learn new mathematical concepts, as it serves as a foundation for more advanced problem-solving skills (Bailey et al., 2018). The low pre-test scores suggest that students may have lacked essential prerequisite skills, such as number sense, arithmetic fluency, and conceptual understanding. This aligns with findings that mathematical difficulties often stem from insufficient mastery of basic skills, leading to struggles in higher-level math tasks (Baker et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the findings underscore the potential role of instructional strategies in shaping students' academic performance. Studies suggest that structured and repetitive practice, such as timed practice drills, can enhance fluency and automaticity in mathematical computations, ultimately leading to improved performance (Knowles, 2010). Fluency-building exercises become effective when consistently reinforced over time, as repeated exposure and retrieval practice strengthen cognitive connections (Chand et al., 2021).

The pre-test findings reinforce the need for targeted interventions to enhance students' mathematical performance. The absence of satisfactory scores in both groups suggest that traditional teaching methods alone may not be sufficient and that additional strategies, such as timed practice drills, should be integrated into instruction.

The results shown on Table 3 imply that timed practice drills are effective in improving students' academic performance in the subject, which aligns with previous studies emphasizing the importance of interventions in mathematics instruction (Knowles, 2010). The results of the study support the notion that fluency and accuracy are foundational skills for success in the subject, as students who struggle recalling basic math facts may find it challenging to answer more complex problems (Bailey et al., 2018).

The observed improvement shown in Table 4 in the TPD group's scores reinforces the effectiveness of timed drills in enhancing mathematical skills, whereas the lack of significant progress in the NTPD group suggests that the usual way of discussion may be insufficient for developing fluency and accuracy in mathematical computations.

Timed practice drills allow learners to master math facts for advancing mathematical thinking by providing ample drill and include immediate and corrective feedback. The structured and repetitive nature of timed drills allows learners to strengthen their retrieval

of math facts. This aligns with the study's findings, where the significant improvement in the TPD group's post-test scores suggests that timed practice drills improves students' academic performance (Fababaer, 2019).

The findings of this study are further supported by Manalaysay (2021), who emphasized that the consistent use of timed drills in mathematics can positively influence the numeracy skills of primary grade learners. The results showed significant improvements in the students' math performance. This suggests that the engagement of the students with mathematics drills, which employed a causal style of discourse, led to better retention of numeracy skills and enabled them to achieve mastery of the lesson.

A similar study conducted by Nelson et al. in 2016 evaluated the importance of growth in math fact skills in relation to students' overall math proficiency. The study found that math facts may retain predictive value for math proficiency and may improve students' academic performance. Similar findings were observed in a study conducted by Lesaca and Falle (2021), which focused on the impact of timed practice drills on the automaticity of students' mathematical operations.

The study found significant differences in the level of performance between pre-test and post-test assessments for the treatment group. Timed practice drills were recommended for use across all grade levels to enhance academic achievement in mathematics. Furthermore, the results align with the study conducted by Lozano (2019), which investigated the effectiveness of timed drills in improving the speed and accuracy of students in solving problems in plane coordinate geometry. Lozano's findings reinforce the idea that the ability to quickly retrieve and apply mathematical knowledge significantly contributes to the overall problem-solving ability.

Conclusions

This study examined the effects of timed practice drills on the academic performance in mathematics of grade 8 learners. Results showed that the level of academic performance in mathematics of the learners has improved when exposed to the timed practice drills compared to those who are not exposed to timed practice drills.

The level of academic performance of students under the NTPD group in both pre-test and post-test assessment falls under "Did Not Meet Expectations". This means that the students performed poorly in both tests. There is no significant improvement in their academic performance when not exposed to timed practice drills.

On the other hand, the level of academic performance of students under the TPD group in the pre-test assessment falls under "Did Not Meet Expectations". In terms of the post-test assessment, the TPD group falls under "Satisfactory". This means that there is a significant improvement in their academic performance when exposed to timed practice drills.

There is a significant difference on the level of academic performance in mathematics between the NTPD and TPD groups in the post-test assessment. The performance of the

TPD has increased significantly compared to the NTPD group. Moreover, the intervention, timed practice drills is effective.

Recommendations

The study's conclusions lead to some recommendations for further research and action. The use of TPD intervention is highly recommended in classroom teaching across all grade levels to improve academic performance especially in mathematics.

Further research could explore other potential factors influencing the academic performance of the students. Academics alone do not appear to be a strong determinant of the academic performance of the students, it is important to broaden the scope of future research. Investigate other factors that may have a more substantial impact on mathematics achievement, such as grade level, teaching methods, curriculum effectiveness, student motivation, or socioeconomic factors.

The study recommends that teachers design and implement an intervention strategy aimed at improving students' performance in mathematics, focusing on the competencies they struggle with the most. Teachers should consistently apply this intervention and expand the range of mathematical competencies being addressed.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirms that this study was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their participation, and they were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were strictly maintained throughout the study. The well-being of all participants was observed, ensuring no harm or discomfort was caused. There is no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study. All sources were properly cited. The interpretation of the findings was conducted without any bias, and the results were used solely for research purposes.

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